

Higher order mode dielectric resonator antenna excited using microstrip line

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the square-shaped dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) operating on higher order ($TE_{\delta 13}$) mode for the fifth generation (5G) communication applications is presented. The proposed DR antenna is excited by using a microstrip feed line and designed at the operating frequency of 28 GHz. The Rogers RT/Duroid 5880 material having a thickness of 0.254mm and a dielectric constant of 2.2 is used for the substrate. The commercial CST microwave studio (CST MWS) is used for the optimization and simulation of the antenna design. The reflection coefficient, antenna gain, radiation efficiency, VSWR and radiation pattern are studied. A -10dB bandwidth of 4.6% (1.3 GHz) for VSWR<2 with a gain of 5 dBi and radiation efficiency of 89%. The proposed antenna design is suitable for future 5G wireless communication applications.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the fast revolution in the telecommunication industry, wireless technology has evolving from first generation (1G) to fifth generation (5G) [1]. In recent years, the increasing number of wireless devices and services have triggered the engineers, scientists, researchers in academia and industries to move on to the future generation (5G) communication technology, which is expected to be introduced by 2020 and beyond. It is an ultimate goal of all scientists and researchers to build a wireless world in which all devices are connected with one another wirelessly. In Today's modern wireless era, antennas with high radiation efficiency, compact size, high gain, and large bandwidth are required [2, 3]. Antennas are an essential part of any wireless communication systems. The two classes of antennas, named microstrip patch antennas (MSA) and dielectric resonator antennas (DRAs) are extensively used in the applications of modern communication. Recently, research antenna community is paying more attention to dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) due to its alluring features of higher radiation efficiency, relatively large impedance bandwidth, low profile, design flexibility, ease of excitation schemes and ease of fabrication [4-12]. In addition, DRA can be excited by different feeding methods like microstrip feed line [13], probe feeding [14, 15], aperture coupling [16, 17], and coplanar waveguide (CPW) [16]. DRA comes in various shapes such as cylindrical [18, 19], rectangular [20, 21], Hemi-spherical [22] and triangular [23, 24]. Thus, DRA is considered as alternative to low gain metallic conventional antennas and is best candidate for the 5G applications [25].

Several methods have been proposed in the literature to improve the bandwidth and gain of DRA antenna, including stacking DRAs [26, 27] and EBG structure [28, 29]. In this paper, dielectric resonator

antenna (DRA) based on higher order $TE_{\delta 13}$ mode using microstrip feed line for gain and bandwidth improvement with high radiation efficiency at millimeter wave frequency (mm-wave) of 28 GHz is presented. A lot of work has been done previously on the fundamental mode at a lower frequency, but a limited work has been done on the higher order mode especially at millimeter wave frequencies. The excitation of higher order mode is simple in structure and does not increase complexity as compared to other techniques mentioned. This paper is organized as follows: The antenna geometry configuration and design process are described in section 2. The results and discussion part of the proposed structure are described in section 3. The conclusion of the paper is given in section 4.

2. ANTENNA GEOMETRY

The resonant frequency f_o of dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) is computed as follows [30]:

$$f_o = \frac{c}{2\pi\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2} \tag{1}$$

Where ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the DRA, c is the speed of light (in free space), k_x, k_y and k_z . Symbols denote the wave number in the x,y and z directions, respectively. The proposed antenna geometry is shown in Figure 1. The antenna is resonating at the operating frequency of 28 GHz. The squared DRA has length, width and height ($a \times b \times d$) with a dielectric constant of ϵ_{rs} . The DRA is placed on the Rogers RT/Duroid 5880 substrate with a thickness of h_s and relative permittivity of ϵ_{rd} . The DRA is excited by using 50Ω microstrip feed line. Table 1 lists the optimized dimensions of the proposed antenna design.

Table 1. Optimized dimensions of the proposed DR antenna, all dimensions are in millimetres (mm)

Parameters	Description	Dimension
L_g	Ground length	20
W_g	Ground width	20
h_g	Ground height	0.0175
L_s	Substrate length	20
W_s	Substrate width	20
h_s	Substrate height	0.254
Substrate ϵ_r	Dielectric constant	2.2
a	DRA length	3.5
b	DRA width	3.5
d	DRA height	5.1
DRA ϵ_r	Dielectric constant	10
L_f	Feed length	9.78
W_f	Feed width	1.65

Figure 1. The geometry of the proposed higher-order mode DRA

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed dielectric resonator antenna design is simulated by CST Microwave studio software. Figure 2 shows the S_{11} of the proposed DRA operating on higher order ($TE_{\delta 13}$) mode at the resonating frequency of 28 GHz. From the figure, the simulated -10 dB impedance bandwidth $S_{11} < -10dB$ of the antenna is 4.6% ($27.3-28.8\text{ GHz}=1.3\text{ GHz}$). The simulated gain and efficiency of an antenna are depicted

in Figure 3. concerning the figure, the DRA shows a gain of 5dBi and high radiation efficiency of 89%. Figure 4 shows the simulated voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) curve as a function of frequency. It is noted that the VSWR is less than 2 for the whole impedance bandwidth. The simulated normalized radiation pattern of the proposed DRA in the E-and H-plane at 28 GHz is shown in Figure 5. The antenna radiates in the broadside direction. Table 2 shows the results of the proposed DR antenna operating on $TE_{\delta 13}$ mode at 28 GHz.

Figure 2. Simulated S_{11} of the proposed DRA

Figure 3. Simulated gain and radiation efficiency versus frequency of the proposed DRA

Figure 4. Simulated VSWR versus frequency of the DRA

Figure 5. Simulated normalized radiation pattern in the E-plane and H-plane at 28 GHz

Table 2. Results of the proposed DRA based on higher order $TE_{\delta 13}$ mode at 28 GHz

Mode	f_o (GHz)	BW (%)	Gain (dBi)	Eff. (%)	VSWR
$TE_{\delta 13}$	28	4.6%	5	89	< 1.2

f_o –Resonant frequency in GHz, BW –Bandwidth in percentage, $Gain$ –Gain in dBi, $Eff.$ –Efficiency in percentage (%), $VSWR$ –Voltage standing wave ratio.

4. CONCLUSION

Higher order mode dielectric resonator antenna excited using microstrip line is presented and investigated. The proposed antenna achieves an impedance bandwidth of 4.6%, for $VSWR < 2$, covering the frequency range from 27.3GHz to 28.8 GHz with a gain of 5dBi and high radiation efficiency of 89%. The proposed antenna is small in size and simple structure which can be used for fifth generation (5G) wireless communication applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Z. N. Zool Ambia, M. H. Jamaluddin, M.R. Kamarudin, J. Nasir, R.R. Selvaraju, "Evolution of H-Shaped Dielectric Resonator Antenna for 5G Applications," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 562–568, February 2019.
- [2] H. A. Ameen, *et al.*, "A 28 Ghz Four-Channel Phased-Array Transceiver in 65-Nm CMOS Technology for 5G Applications," *AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 98, pp. 19–28, January 2019.
- [3] Abinash Gaya, Mohd Haizal Jamaluddin, M. R. Kamarudin, Irfan Ali, "A Wideband Dielectric Resonator Antenna with A Cross Slot Aperture for 5G Communications," *TELKOMNIKA Telecommunication Computer Electronics and Control*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 2218-2225, October 2019.
- [4] I. Ali, M. H. Jamaluddin, A. Gaya, and H. A. Rahim, "A Dielectric Resonator Antenna with Enhanced Gain and Bandwidth for 5G Applications," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1-12, 2020.
- [5] A. Iqbal, A. Smida, O. A. Saraereh, and Q. H. Alsafasfeh, "Cylindrical Dielectric Resonator Antenna-Based Sensors for Liquid Chemical Detection," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 1-9, 2019.
- [6] A. A. Id, J. Jung, Y. Yang, K. Lee, S. Yi, and K. C. Hwang, "A 3-D Meandered Probe-Fed Dual-Band Circularly Polarized Dielectric Resonator Antenna," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 1–11, 2018.
- [7] G. Varshney, V. S. Pandey and R. S. Yaduvanshi, "Dual-band fan-blade-shaped circularly polarised dielectric resonator antenna," in *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 11, no. 13, pp. 1868-1871, 20 10 2017.
- [8] J. Liang and S. Zhang, "Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM) Generation by Cylinder Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Future Wireless Communications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 4, pp. 9570-9574, 2016.
- [9] A. A. Abdulmajid, Y. Khalil and S. Khamas, "Higher-Order-Mode Circularly Polarized Two-Layer Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 1114-1117, June 2018.
- [10] A. Gupta and R. K. Gangwar, "Dual-Band Circularly Polarized Aperture Coupled Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Wireless Applications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 11388-11396, 2018.
- [11] N. H. Shahadan *et al.*, "Steerable Higher Order Mode Dielectric Resonator Antenna With Parasitic Elements for 5G Applications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 22234-22243, 2017.
- [12] I. Ali, M. H. Jamaluddin, M. R. Kamarudin, A. Gaya, and R. Selvaraju, "Wideband and High Gain Dielectric Resonator Antenna for 5G Applications," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1047-1052, September 2019.
- [13] T. A. Denidni and Z. Weng, "Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Ultrawideband Applications," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 45, no. 24, pp. 1210-1212, 19 November 2009.
- [14] Y. Pan, K. W. Leung and K. Lu, "Compact Quasi-Isotropic Dielectric Resonator Antenna With Small Ground Plane," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 62, no. 2, pp. 577-585, Feb. 2014.
- [15] A. Gaya, M. H. Jamaluddin, M. R. Kamarudin, R. Selvaraju and I. Ali, "Performance Analysis of a Dielectric Resonator Antenna with Different Feeding Technique for 5G Communication," *2018 2nd International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (Icon EEI)*, Batam, Indonesia, 2018, pp. 92-97.
- [16] R. Chair, A. A. Kishk and K. F. Lee, "Wideband stair-shaped dielectric resonator antennas," in *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 299-305, April 2007.
- [17] I. Ali, M. H. Jamaluddin, M. R. Kamarudin, A. Gaya, and M. H. Dahri, "Gain Enhancement of Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Millimeter Wave Applications," *TELKOMNIKA Telecommunication, Computing, Electronics and Control*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1670–1673, 2019.
- [18] D. Guha and Y. M. M. Antar, "Four-Element Cylindrical Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Wideband Monopole-Like Radiation," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 2657-2662, Sept. 2006.
- [19] N. K. Mishra, S. Das, and D. K. Vishwakarma, "Beam Steered Linear Array of Cylindrical Dielectric Resonator Antenna," *AEUE - Int. J. Electron. Commun.*, vol. 98, pp. 106–113, January 2019.
- [20] M. W. McAllister, S. A. Long and G. L. Conway, "Rectangular dielectric resonator antenna," in *Electronics Letters*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 218-219, 17 March 1983.
- [21] P. Patel, B. Mukherjee and J. Mukherjee, "A novel pierced rectangular dielectric resonator antenna for wideband communication systems," *2014 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Computing and Communication Technologies (CONECCT)*, Bangalore, pp. 1-5, 2014.
- [22] B. Mukherjee, P. Patel and J. Mukherjee, "A Novel Hemispherical Dielectric Resonator Antenna With Complementary Split-Ring-Shaped Slots and Resonator for Wideband and Low Cross-Polar Applications," in *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 120-128, Feb. 2015.
- [23] H. Y. Lo, K. W. Leung, K. M. Luk and E. K. N. Yung, "Low profile equilateral-triangular dielectric resonator antenna of very high permittivity," in *Electronics Letters*, vol. 35, no. 25, pp. 2164-2166, 9 Dec. 1999.
- [24] S. Maity and B. Gupta, "Experimental Investigations on Wideband Triangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 64, no. 12, pp. 5483-5486, Dec. 2016.
- [25] U. Illahi, J. Iqbal, M. I. Sulaiman, M Alam, M. S. Mazliham, M. H. Jamaluddin, "Circularly Polarized Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna Excited by an Off-Set Conformal Metal Strip," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 902–909, August 2019.

- [26] Y. M. Pan and S. Y. Zheng, "A Low-Profile Stacked Dielectric Resonator Antenna With High-Gain and Wide Bandwidth," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 15, pp. 68-71, 2016.
- [27] A. A. Kishk, Xiao Zhang, A. W. Glisson and D. Kajfez, "Numerical analysis of stacked dielectric resonator antennas excited by a coaxial probe for wideband applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 51, no. 8, pp. 1996-2006, Aug. 2003.
- [28] M. J. Al-Hasan, T. A. Denidni and A. R. Sebak, "Millimeter-Wave EBG-Based Aperture-Coupled Dielectric Resonator Antenna," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 4354-4357, Aug. 2013.
- [29] T. A. Denidni, Y. Coulibaly and H. Boutayeb, "Hybrid Dielectric Resonator Antenna With Circular Mushroom-Like Structure for Gain Improvement," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 1043-1049, April 2009.
- [30] R. Kumar Mongia and A. Ittipiboon, "Theoretical and experimental investigations on rectangular dielectric resonator antennas," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 45, no. 9, pp. 1348-1356, Sept. 1997.

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